

D6.2: ORDP: Open Research Data - Data management plan

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Project acronym	IAWAS
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Author (Company)	Changes to document
21/12/2018	v02.0	SONACA	Initial version
18/01/2018	V02.1	Cranfield University	Inputs from CU
31/01/2019	V01.2	Selectarc	Inputs from Selectarc
14/02/2019	V01.3	UAC	Inputs from UAC
15/04/2019	V02.0	SONACA	Changes performed to adapt D6.2 to CleanSky requirements and template
17/04/2019	V02.1	UAC	Inputs from UAC
09/05/2019	V02.2	Cranfield University	Inputs from CU
09/05/2019	V02.3	Selectarc	Inputs from Selectarc
09/05/2019	V02.4	Lortek	Revised by Topic Manager
10/05/2019	V02.5	SONACA	Annexes explanation in Section 1
10/05/2019	V02.6	Lortek	Approved by the Topic Manager
10/02/2021	V03.0	SONACA	Update of the Project Data Contact
15/12/2022	V04.0	SONACA	Update of the Project Data

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1. Executive summary

This document, D6.2 ORDP: Open Research Data - Data management plan is a deliverable of the IAWAS project launched under the ITD/IADP/TA, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme under Grant Agreement 821371.

The Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) of the European Commission enables open access and reuse of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. There are two main pillars to the Pilot, the first one developing a **Data Management Plan (DMP)** and the second one, **providing open access to research data**.

The conditions to adhere are:

- **Develop (and keep up-to-date) a DMP** – See section 2: DMP
The DMP presented in section 2 will be updated along the project. In order to ensure that all the information about the announced data is in accordance with the produced data, a check is foreseen at least at the end of each WP. If some modifications are needed or there is additional information to implement, an update will be done.
- **Deposit the data in a research data repository** – See Section 2.1.1: Data storage
The documents will be stored in several repositories.
- **Ensure third parties can freely access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate the data** – See section 2.1.2: Data accessibility
IAWAS consortium believes that by enabling access to the data and knowledge of its members, the lifetime and usefulness of their scientific research will be greatly enhanced.
- **Provide related information and identify the tools needed to use the raw data to validate your research** – See section 3: Tools

In the framework of the CleanSky project IAWAS, this report has been issued to explain how the generated data is going to be dealt with and in which way the project is going to be in line with the ORDP approach. The data generated by this project will be related to the main IAWAS goals, LBW and WAAM of Al-Li alloys and the developing of new wire compositions for these purposes. Therefore, we expect to generate data regarding:

- Casting and extruding of the different alloys
- Wire drawing
- LBW testing
- WAAM testing
- LCA related to these process

The detailed data packages can be seen in Section 2.4: Data summary.

Annex I is a table containing the LBW parameters to be recorded for each performed weld to ensure its traceability. This table will be attached to the LBW test results.

Annex II and III contain the dataset archiving template for WAAM and LBW respectively. This template is the one recommended by CleanSky and will be used for the test data generated during the project.

2. DMP

2.1 DMP Internal Consortium Policy

The responsibilities of the DMP will be shared between partners. Each one will be responsible for managing its own data:

- Using a format that eases access and enables the long term usability
- Storing the data in the convenient repositories as soon as possible.
- Making it available to others following Green Open Access rules (under justification Golden Open Access rules can be followed)
- Updating the data whenever necessary

In general, the data shall be available in the following month after the work is finished. When a clear owner is not identified, the responsibility for its management will lie with the Project Data Contact. The adopted strategy for the management of the data is defined in the following sub-sections.

2.1.1 Data storage

The data will be stored in several places to ensure their availability. Formats to save research data will be selected thinking about the long-term usability of the data and choose durable formats that will last for the lifetime of the project, plus a retention period of at least 5 years after the payment of the balance. The repository chosen will depend on the data and its storage will be decided before approval. As general rules:

- All the generated data that is not confidential will be available in IAWAS SharePoint for consortium members and Topic Managers.
- Each of the partners will ensure that all research digital data are stored securely on a central server and in durable formats. Storing master copies of research data files on the hard drive of individual desktop or laptop personal computers will be avoided. Removable media such as USB drives, memory cards, CDs, DVDs will be used as working copies of data but for long-term storage a fast, reliable and easily accessible infrastructure for communication and data management will be needed.
- For open data a certified repository which support open access has been chosen. Zenodo, is an Institutional generic repository to store all the research activities funded or not by the European Commission. It will allow depositing both publications and data, while providing tools to link them.

Decisions about storage for highly confidential or highly sensitive research data should be made on a case-by-case basis, in agreement with the Topic Manager.

Non Digital data will be stored in secured facilities.

Due to some NDA restrictive clauses, Al-Li alloy specimens used for LBW testing might be destroyed after finishing the project if it is demanded by the supplier.

2.1.2 Data accessibility

The generated data can be classified in three groups (Figure 1). The accessibility of each deliverable and data will be evaluated before the official approval of the document.

Figure 1 Types of data

Outline results, showing working methods, potential, concepts and examples of what has been achieved will be used as the basis of scientific and technical publications in reviewed journals and conference papers. Information about the study shall be addressed to the largest number of potentially interested parties.

In this way, several types of audiences will be considered for the exploitation and dissemination activities:

- General public.
- End users: suitable Al alloy filler wire compositions and process implementations that solve the current issues in the WAAM and LBW of Li-containing Al alloys.
- Aeronautical community: the potential of the WAAM process for the manufacturing of complex parts made of new Al alloys and the potential of the LBW as an alternative to the traditional mechanical fastening for the assembly of new Al alloy parts.

The information will be dispatched through newsletter, technical papers and conference presentations, public web site, release in international scientific journals.

An additional dissemination mechanism will be through WAAMMat which is a rolling technology maturation programme aimed at WAAM processes. Cranfield University leads the WAAMMat consortium which has a strong European flavour with more than 25 industrial and 13 academic partners (more info on waammat.com). More detail into dissemination activities will be shortly available on D6.4 Draft Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results.

Nevertheless, the IAWAS project contains some R&D and innovation activities that can require specific protection.

Basic rules which will be used for management of knowledge and intellectual property rights are the following ones:

- Existing results, know-how, software and patents brought as input to the project will remain property of their owner.
- Any publication or communication of any result or know-how acquired during the project will be discussed with the EC and Cleansky representative before release. Research data should be made available as soon as possible. In case of publication an embargo of maximum six months will be sought to give time to publish or seek patents.
- Each party will remain free to patent any or all of its own project results. In case of patent shared by several parties, it is agreed that any communication shall be firstly agreed by all the involved parties and it cannot be done before submitting the patent to the patent office.

In addition, whatever the owner of the submitted patent, it is agreed that inventors or co-inventors are the people who are involved in the invention process.

The IAWAS project will follow EUs rules on open-access to peer reviewed articles. Green Open Access rules will be considered as the first choice. If it is deemed necessary Gold Open Access rules can be also followed. The decision will be made on a case-by-case basis taking into account the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020.

2.2 DATA MANAGEMENT Responsible

The Project Data Contact will be in charge of:

- Ensuring the data is correctly uploaded into the different repositories (mainly IAWAS and Zenodo) through periodical checks
- Completing the DMP with the links leading to the data
- Ensuring the data availability and answering specific requests
- Updating DMP and justifying the changes. This update will be performed at least twice time per year or at the end of each WP.
- Ensuring that all the information about the announced data is in accordance with the produced data
- Communicating with the Topic Manager.

Table 1 Project Data Contact

Project Data Contact (PDC)	Philippe Dufour
PDC Affiliation	SONACA
PDC mail	philippe.dufour@sonaca.com
PDC telephone number	+3271255035

2.3 Data re-use and cost

The data produced in the project will be interoperable. It will be available to be re-used between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. For example, when possible the standard used for testing will be clearly identified. All the published data will be useable by

third parties for an undefined time and it will be available at Zenodo for this purpose. For this same reason, the licenses proposed by Zenodo will be adopted.

It is planned to use Green Open Access Rules, that do not cost any money. Zenodo is also free of charges.

2.4 Data summary

2.4.1 Collected data in WP1

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
Wire new compositions	Chemical compositions casted to produce raw materials bars	Composition analysis - PDF Certificates of conformity	No	UAC	NA	NA	Confidential - sensitive data UAC prior know-how
Wire extrusion	Manufacturing route in order to produce round bars suitable for further drawing	Manufacturing Flow chart PDF	No	UAC	NA	NA	Confidential - sensitive data UAC prior know-how
WAAM test results - Support to D1.1	<p>The specimen will be identified as following:</p> <p>WP1_WAAM_YYYYMMDD_AAAA_X</p> <p>With YYYYMMDD the manufacture date of the specimen, AAAA the wire used and X=1, 2, 3... the specimen number.</p> <p>The parameters used to deposit the samples as well as the results obtained (chemical composition, micro-hardness) for</p>	Samples - pdf	No	CU	NA	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (Data commercially sensitive & IP agreement with WAAM3D)

	each specimen will be provided in a pdf file. DATASET in ANNEX II						
LBW test data - Support to D1.1	<p>LBW parameters will be recorded for each performed weld. The file in Annex I will be filled.</p> <p>Each file will be identified as follows:</p> <p>LBW-WP1-XXXXXX-Y <small>XXXXXX = filler wire; For example AA2196 Y= 1, 2, 3...</small></p> <p>The working parameters that can be varied are: Welding speed, power, focus position, gas type, gas Flow and welding direction (push or pull)</p> <p>Test results assessing the properties of each weld will be also reported in the same file (photos, images, values...)</p> <p>DATASET in ANNEX III</p>	Presentation – Pdf – Excel	No	SONACA	NA	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager - prior know-how
D1.1	<p>Suitable new aluminum alloys for wire manufacturing – ML1</p> <p>This deliverable will contain the first compositions to be casted</p>	Report - Pdf	Yes, deliverable based on former results found in the literature and in the LBW and WAAM test results to	UAC	5.29Mo	Universities, Research Centers End users Aeronautical sector	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – possibility of patenting

			be done with the commercial wire				
Literature review – LBW - Support to D1.1	Literature review of LBW	Report - Pdf	Yes, compilation of results and information in literature	SONACA	1.7Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2623437
Literature review – WAAM - Support to D1.1	Literature review of WAAM	Report - Pdf	Yes, compilation of results and information in literature and of former projects in CU	CU	2.25Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3269805
Literature review – Al-Li alloys - Support to D1.1	Literature review of Al-li alloys	Report - Pdf	Yes, compilation of results and information in literature	UAC	857Ko	Universities, Research Centers	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2649056
Wire drawing specification - Support to D1.1	Comments on drawing operations	Presentation - Pdf	No	Selectarc - UACE	510Ko	Universities, Research Centers	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4542871

2.4.2 Collected data in WP2

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D2.1	Wire material development plan Establishment of the plan for wire drawing	Report - Pdf	No	Selectarc	798Ko	Universities, Research Centers End users	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – prior know-how
D2.2	Delivery of the first batch of new Al filler wires to be used for LBW and WAAM Directly related to ML2	Demonstrator	No	Selectarc	NA	End users	NA
Wire Manufacturing Data related to D2.2	The drawing parameters will be recorded for each grade Parameters followed are: Drawing sequences, heat treatment; tensile test of the wire at each step, difficulties The specimen will be identified with the grade, diameter and lot number defined by Selectarc	Report - Pdf	No	Selectarc	NA	Universities, Research Centers End users	Confidential – sensitive data Selectarc prior know-how
D2.3	Manufacturing and test report of the first batch of new Al filler wires	Report - Pdf	No	Selectarc	773Ko	Universities, Research Centers End users	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – prior know-how

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D2.4	Delivery of the final batch of new Al filler wires Directly related to ML3	Demonstrator	No	Selectarc	NA	End users	NA
Wire Manufacturing Data related to D2.4	The drawing parameters will be recorded for each grade Parameters followed are: Drawing sequences, heat treatment; tensile test of the wire at each step, difficulties The specimen will be identified with the grade , diameter and lot number defined by Selectarc	Report - Pdf	No	Selectarc	NA	End users	Confidential – sensitive data Selectarc prior know-how
D2.5	Manufacturing route modifications and test results leading to the final batch of new Al filler wires	Report - Pdf	No	Selectarc	993Ko	End users	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – prior know-how
D2.6	LCA data of the final batch of new Al filler wires	Report – Pdf – Excel	No	Selectarc	957Ko	EcoTECH End users	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7464232

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
LBW test data	<p>Assessment of the properties of the specimens welded with the new wires</p> <p>LBW parameters will be recorded for each performed weld. The file in Annex I will be filled.</p> <p>Each file will be identified as follows:</p> <p>LBW-WP2-XXXXXX-Y XXXXXX = filler wire; For example AA2196 Y= 1, 2, 3...</p> <p>The working parameters that can be varied are: Welding speed, power, focus position, gas type, gas Flow and welding direction (push or pull)</p> <p>Test results assessing the properties of each weld will be also reported in the same file</p> <p>DATASET in ANNEX III</p>	Presentation – Pdf – Excel	No	SONACA	NA	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – prior know-how

2.4.3 Collected data in WP3

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D3.1	Additive Manufacturing process development and test plan: Establishment of the plan for WAAM	Report - Pdf	No	CU	842Ko	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)
WAAM experimental data related to WP3	<p>The specimen will be identified as following: WP3_WAAM_YYYYMMDD_X</p> <p>With YYYYMMDD the manufacture date of the specimen and X=1, 2, 3...</p> <p>Each day, an excel file (identified as WP3_WAAM_YYYYMMDD) will gather the experimental data used for the samples manufacture. All files used for process monitoring will also be stored (video, thermocouple data, arc characteristics) into a folder identified as WP3_WAAM_YYYYMMDD</p> <p>Experimental data include, but are not limited to, set up configuration, process (Plasma or Metal Gas Arc), process parameters, wire(s) composition, diameter, wire feed speed, laser power, laser beam spot diameter, Travel speed, inter-pass rolling parameters, and heat treatment.</p> <p>The Excel file will also include any results obtained to the sample including, if applicable, micro-hardness measurements, chemical composition analysis, tensile test results, microstructure images, and porosity analysis.</p>	Samples Experimental data – Excel and video files	No	CU	NA	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)

	Definition	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D3.2	<p><u>Optimum specimens manufactured by Additive Manufacturing and post-treated</u></p> <p>First assessment of the properties of the WAAM specimens</p> <p>The specimen will be identified as following: WP3_WAAM_D3.2_X with X=1,2,3...</p> <p>Each sample will go along with an Excel file very similar to what is described above in the section "WAAM data related to D3.2". A PDF report will gather all relevant information and results.</p> <p>Directly related to ML4</p>	<p>Report-PDF</p> <p>Experimental data – Excel and video files</p> <p>Demonstrator</p>	<p>Yes, deliverable based on the data detailed in "WAAM experimental data related to WP3W"</p>	CU	974Ko	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D3.3	<p>Optimization of the Additive Manufacturing and Post-treatment implementation</p> <p>Directly related to ML4</p>	Report - Pdf	<p>Yes, deliverable based on the data detailed in "WAAM data related to WP3W"</p>	CU	5.08Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D3.4	Hybrid WAAM process development update	Report - Pdf	TBD	CU	2.25Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D3.5	Preliminary LCA data for the used manufacturing technologies	Report – Pdf – Excel	No	CU	335Ko	EcoTECH End users	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)

2.4.4 Collected data in WP4

	Purpose	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D4.1	Specimen testing and characterization to assess the properties of the WAAM specimens Directly related to ML5 DATASET in ANNEX II	Report – Pdf – Excel	No	SONACA	3.17Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (CU IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D4.2	Additive Manufacturing process definition for demonstrator manufacturing Directly related to ML5	Report – Pdf –	No	CU	1.44Mo	Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (IP agreement with WAAM3D)

2.4.5 Collected data in WP5

	Purpose	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D5.1	Delivery of the optimized demonstrator manufactured by Additive Manufacturing to TM Directly related to ML6	Catpart/Catproduct .dat/.db	No	SONACA	NA	EcoTECH	Restricted access – Only available for partners and topic manager – SONACA prior know-how
D5.2	Demonstrator manufacturing by Additive Manufacturing Directly related to ML6	Report – Pdf	No	CU	1.44Mo	EcoTECH	Restricted access (CU IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D5.3	Inspection of the demonstrators to assess the properties of the demonstrator Directly related to ML7	Report – Pdf – Excel	No	SONACA	1.68Mo	EcoTECH Universities, Research Centers	Restricted access (CU IP agreement with WAAM3D)
D5.4	LCA data of demonstrator manufacturing by Additive Manufacturing Directly related to ML7	Report – Pdf – Excel	No	CU	4.02Mo	EcoTECH End users	Restricted access (CU IP agreement with WAAM3D)

2.4.6 Collected data in WP6

	Purpose	Format	Re-use data	Origin	Size	Utility	Open access
D6.1	Signature of the CA and the IA	Report-Pdf	No	SONACA	9Ko	Consortium Topic manager	Open access
D6.2	ORDP: Open Research Data - Data management plan	Report-Pdf	No	SONACA	480Ko	Consortium Topic manager	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7510018
D6.3	IPR management plan	Report-Pdf	No	SONACA	1.67Mo	Consortium Topic manager	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7464395
D6.4	Draft Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (draft PDER)	Report-Pdf	No	SONACA	425Ko	Consortium Topic manager	Open access DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7464411
D6.5	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER)	Report-Pdf	Yes, D6.4	SONACA	593Ko	Consortium Topic manager	Open access 10.5281/zenodo.7510005

3. Tools

The foreseen tools needed to access to the data and documents will be

- PDF
- Excel
- SAMCEF
- CATIA

ANNEX I: LBW file

General information	Weld reference	
	Date	
	Welding process	
	Welding direction	
	Welding position	
	Base material type and thermal condition	
	Filler wire material	
	Filler wire - diameter (mm)	
	Joint type	
	Pre-weld cleaning procedure	
	Welding Safety Class: 1, 2 or 3	
	Welding Sensitivity Class: A, B or C	
Equipment	Type of source, model and make,	
	Nominal power,	
	Continuous wave or pulsed,	
	Number of lasers combined	
Measured values for the beam quality parameters	Beam transverse electro-magnetic mode	
	Beam divergence	
	Wavelength	
	Beam polarization and orientation	
	Beam parameter product	
Beam delivery and Focusing System:	Method of transmission	
	Method of beam shaping	
	Distance from beam source to focusing system	
	Beam diameter on entrance to focusing system	
	Focusing optics	
	Focal length	
	Nominal focal spot size and method of measuring	
	Beam path protection system	
Backing and shielding gas	The method and type of backing	
	Backing material and dimensions	
	The composition	
	Shield gas type	
	Shield gas flow rate	
	Location of the shield gas	
	Duration of the shield gas	
	A description, schematic diagram, showing design, position of nozzle(s) for plasma suppression gas in relation to the joint, welding direction and welding point	
	Operation(s) and dimensions of the molten pool protection	
	Location and orientation of the shielding gas nozzle with respect to the workpiece	
Pre-heating and post-weld heat treatment	In case pre-heating is applied, the temperature, and the time at temperature, This includes a description of any other instructions related to the heat treatment.	
	In case a post weld heat treatment is applied, the temperature and the time at temperature shall be included in the WPS This includes a description of any other instructions related to the heat treatment.	
	In the case when the laser beam used for the welded joint is used for preheating or post-weld heat treatment, the relevant parameters for the preheating or post-weld heat treatment shall be recorded	
Others	Tooling and fixtures	

ANNEX II: WAAM test data

Name of IADP/ITD/TA/TE2/Domain	JTI-CS2-2017-CfP07-AIR-01-34
Data Storage	ZENODO
Link to repository	https://zenodo.org/
Dataset Identifier	TBD (DOI)
Relevant Keywords	Al-Li alloys, WAAM
Data Licence	CC BY 4.0
Date for Data Publication	TBD
Date of data collection	TBD
Data Version	Zenodo DOI versioning
Data Preservation time	5 year (2026)
Name of the Data Set Responsible (DSR)	Eloise Eimer
DSR e-mail	e.eimer@cranfield.ac.uk
DSR Telephone	+44 1234 75 5055
Funding body(ies)	European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme.
Grant number	821371
Partner organisations	Cranfield University
Project duration	Start: 2018-10-01 End: 2022-10-31
Date DMP created	21/12/2018
Date last update	15/12/2022

Version	V04
Name of the DMPR (responsibilities for data management of the IADP/ITD/TA/TE2)	<i>Philippe Dufour</i>
DMPR e-mail	philippe.dufour@sonaca.com
DMPR Telephone	+3271255035
Description of the research	<i>Development of new wire compositions for LBW and WAAM of Al-Li alloys</i>
Data Collection	<i>Give a short description of the data, including amount (if known) and content.</i>
Existence of similar data	N/A
Nature of the Data	<i>Experimental data</i>
Data Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>text</i> • <i>numbers</i> • <i>images</i>
Data Format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>.xlsx,</i> • <i>.pdf</i>
Data Size	<i>TBD</i>
Number of files	<i>TBD</i>
Descriptive file	<i>Read_me.pdf</i>
Data File	<i>Input.txt</i>
Quality/Accuracy	<i>TBD</i>
Unit measurement system	<i>SI</i>
Potential Users	<i>Universities, Research Centers</i>
Ethical Issue	<i>NA</i>

ANNEX III: LBW test data

Name of IADP/ITD/TA/TE2/Domain	JTI-CS2-2017-CfP07-AIR-01-34
Data Storage	ZENODO
Link to repository	https://zenodo.org/
Dataset Identifier	TBD (DOI)
Relevant Keywords	Al-Li alloys, LBW
Data Licence	CC BY 4.0
Date for Data Publication	TBD
Date of data collection	TBD
Data Version	Zenodo DOI versioning
Data Preservation time	5 year (2026)
Name of the Data Set Responsible (DSR)	Philippe Dufour
DSR e-mail	philippe.dufour@sonaca.com
DSR Telephone	+3271255035
Funding body(ies)	European Union's H2020 through Clean Sky 2 Programme.
Grant number	821371
Partner organisations	SONACA
Project duration	Start: 2018-10-01 End: 2022-10-31
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DMPR e-mail	philippe.dufour@sonaca.com
DMPR Telephone	+3271255035
Description of the research	<i>Development of new wire compositions for LBW and WAAM of Al-Li alloys</i>
Data Collection	<i>Give a short description of the data, including amount (if known) and content.</i>
Existence of similar data	<i>N/A</i>
Nature of the Data	<i>Experimental data</i>
Data Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>text</i> • <i>numbers</i> • <i>images</i>
Data Format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>.xlsx,</i> • <i>.pdf</i>
Data Size	<i>TBD</i>
Number of files	<i>At least one file for each weld</i>
Descriptive file	<i>Read_me.pdf</i>
Data File	<i>Input.txt</i>
Quality/Accuracy	<i>TBD</i>
Unit measurement system	<i>SI</i>
Potential Users	<i>Universities, Research Centers</i>
Ethical Issue	<i>NA</i>